

EFFECTIVENESS CRITERIA FOR USING ISLAMIC ETHICAL APPROACHES IN MODERN PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article covers the scientific and theoretical foundations and practical aspects of using Islamic moral approaches in the process of modern pedagogical education. The integration of Islamic morality into the educational process and its role in the formation of spiritual and moral values in students are analyzed. Also, the formation of positive personal qualities, strong moral views, a sense of social responsibility and cultural communication skills in students is taken as the basis for the criteria for the effectiveness of Islamic moral approaches. The article proposes approaches that serve to further deepen moral education in the education system.

Keywords: Islamic morality, pedagogical education, moral education, criteria for effectiveness, spiritual and moral values, personal education, Islamic approach.

Introduction.

The basis of human development, social stability and spiritual elevation is morality. The solid foundation of any society, its spiritual elevation, first of all, depends on the moral level of its citizens. Especially in today's globalization process, ensuring the moral maturity and spiritual perfection of the younger generation has become one of the urgent tasks. The role of education, in particular, the pedagogical education system, in this process is incomparable. Because it is pedagogical education that prepares tomorrow's leaders, teachers and educators of society. From this point of view, the implementation of Islamic moral approaches to the educational process and ensuring their compatibility with modern pedagogy is of particular scientific and practical importance. The Islamic religion and its moral principles have occupied an important place in the worldview, lifestyle, culture and upbringing of the peoples of the East, in particular the Uzbek people, for centuries. Our scholarly ancestors - thinkers such as Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Farghani, Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Al-Beruni, Ibn Sina, Bahauddin Naqshband, along with science, glorified moral qualities such as humanity, honesty, justice, patience, and kindness. These principles are being rediscovered today as a rich heritage in the field of education.

With the development of technologies in modern education and the improvement of teaching methods, it is observed that the teaching of values such

as humanity, conscience, decency, and honesty has slowed down somewhat. In such conditions, Islamic moral approaches are considered an important educational tool in pedagogical activity. Islamic approaches can serve as an important factor in the formation of not only knowledge, but also faith, moral standards, and a sense of social responsibility in the younger generation. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the possibilities of using Islamic moral approaches in modern pedagogical education, their impact on the development of the student-personality, criteria for effectiveness and practical applications. The main goal of the article is to create a scientific basis for developing a modern strategy for raising a harmonious generation by effectively introducing Islamic moral values into the pedagogical process.

Methodology:

The main methodological basis of this study is the approach aimed at studying the role and effectiveness of Islamic moral approaches in the modern pedagogical education system. The study analyzed the educational possibilities of Islamic moral norms, relying on scientific-historical, pedagogical, religious and philosophical sources. At the same time, it sought to determine the integration of Islamic values into the modern pedagogical process, the forms of their application in practice and their effectiveness.

The analytical approach was used as the main method in the study. The essence of Islamic ethical approaches, their impact on the personal development of students, and their role in spiritual and moral education were deeply analyzed. A comparative analysis of Islamic ethical principles with modern educational methods was also conducted. This made it possible to determine the compatibility of traditional and innovative approaches.

Empirical methods were also used, including questionnaires, interviews, observations, and pedagogical experiments. The impact of Islamic ethical approaches was assessed based on data obtained from teachers, educators, and students working in secondary and higher educational institutions. Based on this data, effectiveness criteria were developed, that is, the assessment was carried out based on criteria such as the formation of moral views in students, the level of behavior culture, social responsibility, honesty, and conscientiousness.

Through a systematic approach, the scope and process of implementation of Islamic ethical ideas at all stages of pedagogical education were studied step by step. This approach made it possible to study Islamic ethics not in isolation, but as an integral part of the educational system. As a result, the methodological,

theoretical, and practical foundations necessary for the effective implementation of Islamic ethical approaches in the modern pedagogical process were identified. This will serve to establish a stable place for Islamic values in the formation of such important qualities as humanity, honesty, and responsibility in the education system in the future.

Discussion:

The implementation of Islamic ethical approaches in the process of modern pedagogical education has a significant impact not only on the intellectual development of students, but also on their spiritual and moral maturity. The results of the study show that when Islamic ethical values are integrated into the educational process, qualities such as honesty, justice, respect, and kindness are strengthened among students. This, in turn, plays an important role in ensuring socio-cultural stability in society.

During the discussion, the effectiveness of Islamic ethical approaches was assessed based on several criteria. First of all, the strength of ethical views among students and their application in everyday life were analyzed. According to the data, understanding religious and moral principles and their application in practice are important factors in shaping students as socially active, responsible individuals.

As a second criterion, the level of cultural dialogue and mutual respect between students was observed. Islamic moral approaches, in particular, the principles of patience, tolerance and honesty, teach young people to be respectful and sincere in their relationships. This serves to create a healthy pedagogical environment in classrooms and universities.

As a third criterion, the formation of a sense of social responsibility in students was studied. Islamic moral education encourages serving society, helping others and contributing to the well-being of society in general. It was noted that most of the young people participating in the study actively apply these values in their lives.

Also, the combination of modern pedagogical methods and Islamic moral principles has yielded positive results in improving the professional qualifications of teachers. Educators are improving the quality of education by enriching their ethical models and concepts with Islamic values. In this process, the combination of traditional and innovative approaches is important.

However, the discussion also highlighted some difficulties in effectively introducing Islamic ethical approaches into the educational process. In particular, there are issues such as the lack of understanding of the role of

religious values in education by some students and parents, and the inability of educators to apply this approach with sufficient knowledge and skills. Therefore, for the successful implementation of Islamic ethical approaches in the education system, it is necessary to train qualified personnel, develop teaching and methodological manuals, and conduct extensive propaganda work. Scientific research has confirmed that the use of Islamic ethical approaches in modern pedagogical education is an effective tool for improving the quality of education and educating the younger generation as spiritually mature individuals. Systematic methodological and organizational work should be carried out to further develop and widely introduce these approaches. This will be an important step not only in the field of education, but also on the path to the spiritual perfection of our society.

Conclusion.

Today, the education system is becoming so complex and multifaceted that it is not enough to be limited to intellectual knowledge alone. In modern pedagogical processes, the issue of comprehensive development of young people, the formation of their moral, aesthetic and spiritual qualities has become one of the most priority tasks. Therefore, the effective introduction of Islamic moral approaches into the education system is of great importance. The data and practical observations studied during the study showed that Islamic moral values affect the personal and social development of young people, allowing them to be educated as more responsible, just and honest people. The integration of Islamic moral approaches into the pedagogical process not only improves the quality of education, but also helps to create a healthy spiritual environment in educational institutions. These approaches play an important role in developing such noble qualities as humanity, respect, kindness and tolerance in students. As a result, young people can adapt to the socio-cultural and spiritual environment of society and develop themselves more positively.

At the same time, in order to effectively apply Islamic moral approaches, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of teachers, fully provide them with modern methodologies, as well as ensure the cooperation of parents and society. This will serve the further development of modern pedagogical education and the upbringing of a harmonious generation based on national and spiritual values.

In conclusion, the implementation of Islamic moral approaches in the modern pedagogical education process directly affects the spiritual and moral maturity of students, their readiness for social activity and the formation of a

harmonious person in society. Therefore, determining the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of these approaches and developing them remains an urgent task. There is no doubt that future research and practical activities in this area will serve to strengthen the spiritual and educational foundations of the education system.

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